

Does L1 Morphology Actually Influence 'Passive' Unaccusatives?: A Corpus Study of
Unaccusative Errors by Japanese Learners
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Second language (L2) learners of English regardless of their first language (L1) backgrounds frequently produce and accept ungrammatical passive sentences with one type of intransitive verb, namely, unaccusative verbs such as Miki was disappeared. A number of previous studies have attempted to reveal the culprit of the unique phenomenon without reaching a consensus. This study critically reviews one of the major accounts for the ungrammatical passivization, L1 morphological transfer, which claims that L1 morphology with unaccusative verbs leads learners to generate and accept 'passive' unaccusatives. According to the analysis, since Japanese has morphological differences between unaccusatives and their transitive counterparts (e.g., English gather/gather, Japanese atum-e-ru/atum-ar-u), Japanese learners of English seek an equivalent and add passive morphology be + en to unaccusatives. If the analysis is on the right track, there is no wonder that Japanese learners add progressive morphology -ing to unaccusatives although unaccusatives in the progressive structure are grammatical. The present study hypothesizes that Japanese speakers produce unaccusatives in the progressive as well as in the passive. This research tests the hypothesis by analyzing a large corpus data that consists of approximately 70,000 words obtained from Japanese learners of English in junior and senior high schools. The findings in the study showed that unaccusatives appeared in the passive structures, yet few in the progressive structures. Therefore, the results demonstrated that L1 morphology has weak or no effects on 'passive' unaccusatives. From the analysis of the corpus, this study concluded that learners are likely to produce 'passive' unaccusatives due to the resemblance between unaccusatives and passives in terms of sentence structures.